

Unlocking the potential exploring pharmacological properties from Apiaceae family

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Abstract

The Apiaceae family, which encompasses a variety of economically important vegetables, herbs, and spices, stands out as one of the largest plant families. Crops such as anise, fennel, carrot, coriander, and parsley are not only valued for their culinary uses but also serve as important sources of botanical flavors and fragrances. Members of the Apiaceae family are known for their diverse medicinal properties, including antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects, as well as benefits for diabetes management and liver protection. In addition, these plants produce a number of unique, specialized metabolites such as volatile phenylpropanoids, furanocoumarins, sesquiterpene coumarins, polyacetylenes, and phthalides. Some of these compounds are rare phytochemicals found exclusively in this family, highlighting their potential for bioprospecting. The objective of this review is to support future research on Apiaceae by providing up-to-date information on their key characteristics, origin and traditional uses. It also collects and analyses the scattered information available in the literature on the chemical composition and biological activities of essential oils and various extracts from selected Apiaceae species, demonstrating their potential for pharmaceutical, cosmetic and other industrial applications.

Keywords

Apiaceae, chemical composition, pharmacology, antimicrobial, antioxidant

Introduction

Researchers around the world are increasingly focusing on medicinal and aromatic plants, recognizing them as a vital source of raw materials for the pharmaceutical, cosmetic, flavor, and fragrance industries. Despite advances in the development of synthetic drugs, a significant proportion of modern medicines are still produced from plants, using modern technology to improve on tradi-

tional methods (Canter et al. 2005). The Apiaceae family stands out as one of the most significant groups of flowering plants, encompassing 3,780 species in 434 genera. The family is found worldwide, predominantly in northern temperate zones and at high altitudes in tropical regions. While Apiaceae (commonly known as Umbellifers) are found almost everywhere, Asia boasts the highest diversity with 289 genera, of which 177 are endemic. Europe and Africa follow with 126 and 121 genera, respectively (Plun-

kett et al. 2018). Notable economically valuable plants of the Apiaceae family include celery (*Apium graveolens*), carrot (*Daucus carota*), Indian pennywort (*Centella asiatica* L. Urb), parsley (*Petroselinum crispum*), parsnip (*Pastinaca sativa*), wild celery (*Angelica archangelica*), coriander (*Coriandrum sativum*), caraway (*Cuminum cyminum*), fennel (*Foeniculum vulgare*), anise (*Pimpinella anisum*), dill (*Anethum graveolens*), and cumin (*Carum carvi*) (Tamokou et al. 2017; Geoffriau and Simon 2020). The Apiaceae family is characterized by several notable features: they are aromatic herbs with alternate leaves that have sheathed bases, hollow stems, and small flowers. Their inflorescences can be simple or compound umbels, and they produce indehiscent fruits or seeds that contain oil ducts (Christensen and Brandt 2006). This family is particularly known for its unique aromas, which arise from secretory cavities filled with resin, oil, or mucilage found in the fruits, stems, leaves, and roots (Berenbaum 1990). Apiaceae includes many economically significant aromatic plants that serve a variety of purposes such as culinary use (spices and seasonings), ornamental use, and medicinal use. These plants are an integral part of industries such as food, perfume, pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and cosmeceutical (Shelef 2003; Saleem et al. 2017; Ngahang Kamte et al. 2018; Önder et al. 2020). Traditionally, many species of Apiaceae have been used as home remedies for a range of health problems (Khare 2008). In ethnomedicine, several plants from this family are used as home remedies for disorders related to the digestive, endocrine, reproductive, and respiratory systems (Aćimović and Kostadinović 2015). The Apiaceae family includes many spices that have been used worldwide for flavoring, seasoning, and coloring, as well as for preservation, since ancient civilizations, especially in India, China, and numerous countries in Southeast Asia. This botanical family is rich in phytochemicals and secondary metabolites that serve as promising sources for pharmaceuticals, including terpenoids, triterpenoid saponins, flavonoids, coumarins, polyacetylenes, and steroids. Furthermore, many species in this family are known for their rich essential oils, which contain over 760 different constituents from various chemical classes, all of which are of significant pharmaceutical interest (Nguyen et al. 2015). Recent studies have further established that Apiaceae species are excellent sources of bioactive phytochemicals, displaying potent antioxidant, antibacterial, antibiotic, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties, as well as antidiabetic and hepatoprotective effects, among others (Rathore et al. 2013; Khalil et al. 2016). Previous studies on plant materials from the Apiaceae family highlight their potential as natural agrochemicals (Pandey et al. 2012). On the other hand, some Apiaceae species, such as *Conioselinum*, are poorly studied, providing a rationale for further research on the subspecies of this fascinating family in terms of medicinal properties. Considering their significant medicinal value, this review was compiled to investigate the phytochemical components of the Apiaceae family and their diverse pharmacological activities.

Method

We conducted a literature search in scientific engines such as Google Scholar, Scopus, Science Direct, Clarivate, Wiley Online, PubMed, and MDPI to investigate the extracts of Apiaceae family, as well as its medicinal properties, such as antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, antioxidant, hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic properties. For the search, the names of most species of the Apiaceae family were used, such as *Eryngium*, *Ferula*, *Angelica*, *Ligusticum*, Fennel etc. with the addition of the name of the pharmacological activities like “*Eryngium* extracts”, “antibacterial characteristics of *Ferula*”, “hepatoprotective activity of *Angelica*”, “antioxidant properties of *Ligusticum*”, “hypoglycemic properties of Fennel”, “hypolipidemic effects of *Coriandrum*” and “medicinal uses” were utilized as keywords.

Chemical composition

Various groups of metabolites were identified in the plant extracts of Apiaceae family obtained from the aerial parts including stems, leaves and inflorescences using solvents such as ethanol, water, methanol and hexane. These extracts were qualitatively analyzed to detect the presence of compounds such as flavonoids, tannins, terpenoids and saponins. Furthermore, advanced techniques such as gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) and high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) were used for accurate detection, quantification and identification of these metabolites in the extracts.

Phenolic compounds and flavonoids

The UV-Vis method stands out as a reliable and cost-effective approach to assess the concentrations of various compounds in solutions. Total phenolic compounds (TPC), total flavonoids (TF) and total terpenoids (TT) were quantified in *E. carlinae* extracts, revealing TPC at 0.0038 mg GAE/mL, TF at 3.3032 mg QE/mL and TT at 0.0424 mg linalool equivalents/mL. In contrast, other studies reported significantly higher TPC levels for the same species, reaching 2.5 mg GAE/mL, while TF was noted below 0.2 mg QE/mL (Cárdenas-Valdovinos et al. 2023). Another study found TPC at 4.33 mg GAE/g dry weight and total saponins at 62.2 mg/g dry weight in the ethanol extract of *E. comosum*. Furthermore, the presence of phenolic compounds and saponins was confirmed in both 50% and 70% ethanol extracts of *E. comosum*, with the 70% extract showing the highest concentrations (Díaz Alvarado 2020). Phenolic acids, especially caffeic, rosmarinic, and chlorogenic acids, are common compounds found in the genus *Eryngium* (Meyer 2010). The researchers used HPLC to study the ethanol extract of *E. longifolium*, successfully identifying these acids, with rosmarinic acid standing out as the most significant. They also observed minor peaks associated with isoflavones and glycosylated flavonoids (Andrade-Cetto et al. 2021). In a similar vein, the same phenolic acids were detected

in aqueous extracts of *E. cymosum* (Espinoza-Hernández et al. 2021). Further analysis confirmed that chlorogenic and rosmarinic acids were abundant in both aqueous and methanol extracts, while caffeic and protocatechuic acids were more concentrated in butanol extracts. Additionally, the flavonoid kaempferol-3-O-(2,6-di-O-trans- ρ -coumaryl)- β -D-glucopyranoside was identified in *E. cymosum*, which is associated with its hypoglycemic properties (Romero-Pérez et al. 2022). An aqueous extract of the aerial parts of *E. carlinae* was analyzed by HPLC-DAD-MS at detection wavelengths of 280, 320, and 370 nm, focusing on 1% and 2% infusion and decoction extracts for 5 and 10 min. This analysis revealed the presence of hydroxybenzoic acids, predominantly gallic acid (1300–2600 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, RT = 12.5 min), as well as smaller amounts of 4-hydroxybenzoic and protocatechuic acids. Hydroxycinnamic acids such as chlorogenic acid (400–700 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, RT = 2.1 min), rosmarinic acid (40–58 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, RT = 25 min) and caffeic acid (12–21 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, RT = 16.3 min) were also detected, as well as smaller amounts of ellagic, p -coumaric, ferulic and sinapic acids. Flavanols such as gallic catechin gallate (600–1600 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, RT = 20.4 min) and flavonols such as quercetin (89–179 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, RT = 25.5 min) were present, as well as trace amounts of flavanones and hydroxybenzaldehydes (Montes-Moreno 2019). Phytosterols including β -sitosterol and stigmasterol were detected, potentially helping in regulating cholesterol levels. Glycosylated saponins with anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties were also identified (López-Luengo 2005).

Terpenes

Researchers have documented the presence and amount of terpenes and sesquiterpenes found in hexane extracts of *E. carlinae* inflorescences from Mexico. Among the predominant components identified were (Z) β -farnesene at 38.79%, β -pinene at 17.53%, calamenene at 13.30%, and α -farnesene at 10.38%. The study found that farnesene and pinene play a significant role in mitigating lipid peroxidation and protein carbonylation, likely enhanced by synergistic interactions with other compounds present in the extract (Peña-Montes et al. 2019). Furthermore, another study identified 21 terpenoid compounds in ethanol extracts obtained from *E. carlinae* leaves and inflorescences. The key terpenoids isolated were borneol (367 mg/L), α -pinene (278 mg/L), myrcene (256 mg/L), caryophyllene (225 mg/L) and β -pinene (120 mg/L). The results also showed differences in the presence and concentration of these compounds at different phenological stages of the plant, particularly before, during and after flowering and fruiting. Notably, extracts from leaves and inflorescences during and after the flowering phase showed the highest levels of metabolites, while pinene and farnesene isomers remained constant throughout these stages (Espino-Garibay 2010). Well-known genera such as *Ferula* and *Peucedanum* offer a variety of chemicals with potential pharmaceutical applications. For example, C17 polyacetylenes in vegetables such as carrot and celery exhibit anticancer properties, especially against

leukemia, as well as anti-inflammatory effects. Psoralen, a linear furanocoumarin, is used to treat skin conditions such as eczema and psoriasis by oral administration and UV-A therapy. However, the family also includes toxic species such as parsley and poison hemlock, which contain potent neurotoxins such as cicutoxin and coniine. *Conium maculatum*, known for its strong toxicity, has been associated with chronic teratogenic effects in livestock and humans. The carrot family is characterized by a limited number of alkaloid-producing species, and these compounds are distributed rather unevenly among them (Sousa et al. 2021).

Volatile compounds

GC-MS method serves as an invaluable resource for the identification of volatile and semi-volatile compounds found in plant tissues. In particular, various aromatic aldehydes, sesquiterpenes and fatty acids have been identified in root, stem, leaf and flower extracts of different *Eryngium* species using GC-MS method. Notable components include 2-dodecenal, 2,4,6-trimethylbenzaldehyde, d-elemene, α -bisabolol, α and β -selinene and fatty acids such as palmitic and stearic acid (Rojas-Silva et al. 2014). These compounds are distributed in many *Eryngium* species worldwide, and their role in biological activities such as antiprotozoal, antibacterial, antifungal, antioxidant, and antidiabetic effects have been documented (Darriet et al. 2012; Paw et al. 2022).

Essential oil

Essential oils and oleoresins can be obtained from the roots, herbs, and fruits of various Apiaceae species. Among the best-known products of this family are the essential oils of coriander, extracted from both the fruits and leaves, as well as the essential oils of sweet and bitter fennel fruits and the essential oils of dill, obtained from its fruits and leaves (Das et al. 2023). Other well-known species include celery, caraway, anise, ajowan, parsley, cumin, carrot, and angelica. Research has identified about 18 Apiaceae species in the Greek flora that have potential for industrial production of essential oils, with estimated yields ranging from 11 to 35 liters per hectare (Palumbo et al. 2021). About 160 different chemical compounds have been detected in the essential oils obtained from various *Ferula* species. The chemical components can be divided into several groups: monoterpene hydrocarbons, which include limonene, myrcene, γ -terpinene, p -cymene, δ -3-carene, α -pinene, and β -pinene; oxygenated monoterpenoids such as α -terpinyl acetate, linalool, sabinene, α -terpineol, verbenone, neryl acetate, and ar-curcumen; sesquiterpene hydrocarbons such as germacrene B and D, β -caryophyllene, (E)-caryophyllene, bicyclogermacrene, α -gurjunene, γ -elemene, γ -cadinene, and δ -cadinene; oxygen-containing sesquiterpenoids including α -cadinol, caryophyllene oxide, guaial, α -eudesmol, (Z)-ocimene, (E)-nerolidol, (E)-ocimene, viridiflorol, carotol, epi- α -muurolol, quinesol, valerianol, and spathulenol; and finally sulfur-containing metabolites such as dimethyl trisulfide, (E)-1-propenyl sec-butyl disulfide,

sec-butyl-(Z)-propenyl disulfide, di-sec-butyl disulfide, phenol 2-methyl-5-(1-methylethyl), sec-butyl-(E)-propenyl disulfide, 2,5-diethylthiophene, trimethylthiophene and 1-methylpropyl-(1E)-prop-1-en-1-yl disulfide, as well as bis-[(1-methylthio)propyl] disulfide and 1-methylpropyl-(Z)-prop-1-en-1-yl disulfide (Sonigra and Meena 2021).

Oligosaccharides and polyalcohols

Furthermore, the researchers identified various oligosaccharides and polyalcohols in the extracts of *E. carlinae* leaves and stems. The extracts contained D-(–)-fructopyranose, D-(–)-tagatofuranose, and sucrose, as well as the polyalcohol 1,5-anhydro-d-sorbitol and cinnamic acid. The authors suggested that the anti-inflammatory effects observed *in vivo* in the extract could be due to the presence of cinnamic acid (Cárdenas-Valdovinos et al. 2023). In the Apiaceae family, the researchers identified a total of 103 polyacetylenes from 41 different genera. The main representatives of this diversity are *Aegopodium*, *Angelica*, *Bupleurum*, *Cicuta*, *Heracleum*, *Ligusticum*, *Oenanthe*, *Peucedanum*, *Pituranthos*, and *Seseli*. Typically, polyacetylenes obtained from higher plants have a linear C17 chain. However, there are also examples of shorter chains such as C10, C13, C14, C15, C16 and C18 chains. In addition, several compounds with chains longer than C18 have been documented. Among the most significant acetylenic metabolites found in plants of the Apiaceae family are falcarinol, falcariindiol-3-acetate, falcarinone, falcarinolone and falcariindione (Christensen and Brandt 2006; Chen et al. 2015).

Figure 1. Chemical structure of biological active compounds of Apiaceae family plants.

Antioxidant activity

Comparative analysis of antioxidant activity conducted using iron reducing ability of plasma (FRAP) assay and Fe_2^+ ion reduction assay revealed that methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane, chloroform, hexane and aqueous ex-

tracts of cumin seeds demonstrated antioxidant properties. Notably, non-volatile extracts exhibited dose-dependent DPPH radical scavenging activity with methanol extract showing the highest inhibition percentage (Thiviyaya et al. 2021). In contrast, ethyl acetate extract exhibited the most significant superoxide radical scavenging activity with an IC_{50} value of 18.3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The aqueous extract could inhibit 50% of superoxide radicals with only 105 μg and cumin root extracts also exhibited notable DPPH radical scavenging activity from various secondary metabolites. Oils from caraway seed extracts exhibit strong antioxidant properties, with the essential oil exhibiting significantly higher activity than standard antioxidants. This is attributed to key compounds such as carvone, linalool, and phenols. Caraway essential oil demonstrated superior 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging ability compared to butylated hydroxyanisole (BHA) and butylated hydroxytoluene (BHT), achieving an inhibition percentage of 85.4% at a concentration of 240 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. This efficacy may be due to the presence of significant amounts of antioxidant compounds including cuminal, γ -terpinene, pinocarveol, carotol, and linalool (Sayed-Ahmad et al. 2021). Blends of caraway and coriander essential oils exhibit better antioxidant properties than individual oils (Yakoubi et al. 2020). In addition, caraway essential oil showed significant antioxidant effects in DPPH assay with an IC_{50} of 15 ± 0.23 mg/mL , although it was less effective than BHT and ascorbic acid. Caraway essential oil had 2.95–3.2 times higher oxidation-reduction properties than these standards and demonstrated 4.7 times higher chelating capacity than EDTA ($IC_{50} = 32.50 \pm 1.32$ mg/mL). There was no significant difference in its ability to inhibit linoleic acid oxidation compared to BHT (Ghannay et al. 2022). A study of the antioxidant activity of ripe and crushed caraway fruits found that at a concentration of 50 mg/mL , caraway essential oil neutralized 90% of DPPH radicals after 40 minutes, with an EC_{50} of 4.6 mg/mL , although it was still weaker than L-ascorbic acid and BHT. The antioxidant properties of caraway essential oil are largely due to its high content of carvone (58.2%), an oxygen-containing monoterpene (Gajić et al. 2020).

Studies on the antioxidant properties of extracts obtained from coriander seeds, leaves and stems using various bioassays such as DPPH free radical scavenging activity assay and iron reducing antioxidant capacity (FRAP) test show that ethanol, methanol and aqueous extracts from leaves exhibit significantly higher antioxidant activities compared to seed extracts. Specifically, at a concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the radical scavenging activities of methanol extracts from seeds and leaves were recorded to be 64.4% and 72.2%, respectively. This remarkable activity is attributed to the elevated levels of carotenoids found in coriander leaves (Que et al. 2019). Interestingly, the essential oil extracted from coriander seeds exhibits superior radical scavenging capabilities compared to that from leaves, the difference being attributed to the higher concentration of linalool in the seed oil (Li et al. 2018). The study by Jay et al. demonstrated the antioxidant potential of *Coriandrum sativum*

L. seed essential oil, showing 66.2% inhibition compared to 87.8% for ascorbic acid, with IC_{50} values of 0.147 mg/mL for seed oil and 0.108 mg/mL for ascorbic acid. DPPH assay revealed 66.48% radical scavenging activity for 500 μ g of coriander seed oil, which was higher than 56.73% of coriander leaf oil. FRAP assay revealed absorbance values of 0.734 for seed oil and 0.815 for leaf oil. According to the study by Kačániová et al. (2020), the radical scavenging activity of coriander EO was 51.05% of the inhibition of acquired EO. EO distilled from the aerial parts of coriander has greater efficacy in antioxidant activity (Raveau et al. 2021). Recent studies tested coriander EO as an antioxidant in cakes and suggested it as a suitable alternative to synthetic antioxidants for food preservation. Moreover, salami supplemented with coriander EO reduced lipid oxidation; therefore, EO increased shelf life (Kačániová et al. 2020). The concentration of 0.1 g/mL EO has the ability to scavenge free radicals (DPPH and galvinoxyl), which is effective in preventing oxidative damage in lipid-containing foods. It acts as a natural substitute for synthetic antioxidants such as BHA, BHT, TBHQ and propyl gallate, which are used in the food industry (Al-Khayri et al. 2023).

Aqueous and ethanol extracts of anise possess greater antioxidant activity than standard antioxidants such as BHA, BHT, and α -tocopherol as demonstrated by various antioxidant assays including DPPH radical scavenging, superoxide anion scavenging, hydrogen peroxide scavenging, and metal chelation. Among six other fruits of the Apiaceae family, anise fruit extracts stood out for their exceptional antioxidant activity as confirmed by DPPH radical scavenging assay (Jangra et al. 2017). In another study, anise EO demonstrated DPPH scavenging activity of 88.3% at 1000 μ g/mL, which is comparable to ascorbic acid (97.40%) and catechin (93.96%). The IC_{50} values for anise essential oil were 14.26 μ g/mL for catechin and 17.21 μ g/mL for ascorbic acid (Ouis and Hariri 2021). Furthermore, at concentrations of 10 and 20 μ L/mL, anise essential oil showed antioxidant activities of 36.02% and 43.62%, respectively, with the highest activity of 77.58% at 50 μ L/mL (El-Sayed et al. 2022).

Dill extracts exhibited strong antioxidant properties assessed by DPPH radical scavenging and β -carotene bleaching methods. The ethanolic extract of dill flowers outperformed the extracts from seeds and leaves, presumably due to higher phenolic content. The aqueous extract also showed significant dose-dependent activity with inhibition rates of 87.5% and 89.7% at 400 μ g/mL in β -carotene linoleate and DPPH assays, respectively (Shyu et al. 2009; Ramadan et al. 2013b). Similarly, parsley extracts exhibit notable antioxidant properties with the essential oils exhibiting EC_{50} values of 5.1 mg/mL in β -carotene assay and 80.2 mg/mL in DPPH assay, which is attributed to apiole and myristicin. Methanolic extract from parsley stems and leaves also exhibit antioxidant effects in various assays. A clinical study with 14 participants found that adding parsley leaves to their diet significantly increased levels of antioxidant enzymes, with apigenin identified as the key active component (Farzaei et al. 2013; Tang et al. 2015).

EO obtained from celery leaves was tested for antioxidant activity both *in vitro* and *in silico* and showed that the DPPH-induced free radical scavenging capacity of EO ranged from 1.580% \pm 0.21% to 32.45% \pm 0.2% over the concentration range of 0.25 mg/mL to 5 mg/mL. Furthermore, the absorption levels in ferric chloride increased from 0.043 \pm 0.01 to 0.279 \pm 0.02 as the concentration increased from 0.25 mg/mL to 5 mg/mL. Notably, the antioxidant activity of celery EO was found to be lower than that of ascorbic acid, which served as the reference standard (Foudah et al. 2021). In a separate study, the composition and antioxidant efficacy of celery seed essential oil studied in twelve populations of *Apium graveolens* L. obtained from Iran revealed variability in antioxidant activity among different seed essential oils, especially between populations from Urmia (P12) and Sanandaj (P1) regions. It was also highlighted that the plant part used for the extraction of the essential oil significantly affects its antioxidant activity. Also, a similar separate study evaluating the antioxidant properties of celery leaf essential oil (EO) showed DPPH free radical scavenging capacity ranging from 1.580% \pm 0.21% to 32.45% \pm 0.2% at concentrations ranging from 0.25 mg/mL to 5 mg/mL (Salimi et al. 2022). It was also found that irradiation enhanced the antioxidant activity of the oil, peaking at 10.0 kGy with percentages of 88.30%, 90.51%, and 93.86% for 10, 15, and 25 μ g oil concentrations, respectively. The control samples showed lower percentages of 77.15%, 81.35%, and 84.09% at the same concentrations. The IC_{50} values for the essential oil ranged from 54.17 μ g/g in the control to 127.23 μ g/g under 5.0 kGy irradiation (Hossam et al. 2020).

A study by Ahmed et al. on the antioxidant properties of fennel seed essential oil from Egypt and China showed significant DPPH radical scavenging activity with an IC_{50} of 15.66 mg/g for Chinese oil, while the Egyptian oil had minimal activity (IC_{50} 141.82 mg/g), indicating geographical differences (Ahmed et al. 2019). Another study found that the antioxidant potential of fennel essential oil varied, with IC_{50} values ranging from 11.83 to 36.90 mg/mL in DPPH assay. Fennel fruit essential oil extracted by microwave-assisted hydrodistillation had an IC_{50} of 14.05 μ L/mL in DPPH assay, which was superior to traditional hydrodistillation (18.58 μ L/mL) due to higher concentrations of oxygenated compounds (Chen et al. 2020). A similar study evaluated the DPPH radical scavenging capacity of fennel essential oil, finding that stem oil (2.58 mg/mL) had higher antioxidant activity compared to leaf oil (6.91 mg/mL), presumably due to its higher phenolic content. Furthermore, essential oils from different parts of the fennel plant showed different antioxidant capacity, with leaves exhibiting the highest activity, followed by umbels and seeds (Milenković et al. 2022). *P. saxifrage* EO had an IC_{50} for DPPH radical scavenging of 6.81 μ g/mL and an EC_{50} for iron reduction of 35.20 μ g/mL, with an IC_{50} for β -carotene of 206 μ g/mL (Nasir and Yabalak 2021). Also, essential oils from *P. tragi-*um flowers and stems showed greater antioxidant potential than gallic acid when tested using DPPH and FRAP assays. Fennel seed essential oil has even stronger antioxidant

properties associated with its high content of polyphenols and flavonoids, including several caffeoylquinic acids and rosmarinic acid (Sharma et al. 2021).

Antibacterial and antifungal properties

Numerous studies have demonstrated potent antibacterial properties of cumin essential oil against various Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, with minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) against *M. tuberculosis* ranging from 6.3 to 25 µg/mL attributed to cumin aldehyde (Derakhshan et al. 2008). It also shows significant antifungal activity against *P. boydii* (88.2%) and *A. flavus* (66.7%) (Rahman and Choudhary 2000). Furthermore, ethanol extracts from cumin seeds exhibit antibacterial effects against *Helicobacter pylori*, with MIC₉₀ values of 0.075 mg/mL (Nostro et al. 2005). Essential oils of caraway seeds also possess antibacterial properties, with MIC values of 0.6% against *E. coli* and 0.5% against *S. aureus*, and minimum bactericidal concentrations (MBC) of 0.8% and 0.6%, respectively (Iacobellis et al. 2004; Mohsenzadeh 2007). Key components such as carvone, limonene, and linalool contribute to these effects. Furthermore, ethanol extracts from caraway seeds inhibit the growth of *Lactobacillus* (Damasius et al. 2007) and show significant antifungal activity against mycotoxigenic *Aspergillus* species, making them potential agents for the control of aflatoxins in food and feed (Razzaghi-Abyaneh et al. 2009; Skrinjar et al. 2009).

Studies show that fennel has significant antibacterial properties. Fennel stem extracts inhibited *B. subtilis*, *A. niger*, and *C. cladosporioides* with MIC values of 25, 250, and 125 µg/mL, respectively. Its aqueous extracts also inhibited *A. radiobacter* pv. *tumefaciens*, *E. carotovora*, *P. fluorescens*, and *P. glycinea*. Fennel essential oil is particularly effective with MIC and MBC values of 1% and 2% against *E. coli* and 2% and 4% against *S. aureus*, although it is less effective against *B. cereus* and *P. aeruginosa*. Fennel essential oil also exhibits antifungal activity, achieving complete inhibition at 6 µL. Aqueous extracts from fennel seeds exhibit significant antifungal effects compared to grisofulvin (Rafieian et al. 2024).

Coriander leaf essential oil inhibits various bacterial strains, while coriander seed oil is effective against 25 strains with MIC values averaging 4.2 µg/mL, mainly due to the high linalool content. MFCs of coriander seed oil against *Candida* species range from 31.2 to 62.5 µg/mL (Mandal and Mandal 2015). Anise essential oil and methanolic extracts exhibit significant antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, and *Proteus vulgaris*. Aqueous and methanolic extracts at 50% concentration were effective against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, with the aqueous extract being the most effective. Anise extracts have also shown significant antifungal activity, particularly against *C. albicans*, with MIC values ranging from 17% to 20% (Akhtar et al. 2008; Al-Bayati 2008; Yazdani et al. 2009).

Parsley leaf extracts, both hot and cold, show significant antibacterial activity against pathogens such as *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Streptococcus*

pyogenes, which are commonly found in burn infections. Methanolic extracts from parsley leaves also show antimicrobial activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *P. aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *S. aureus*, and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, with coumarins identified as the active compounds. In addition, parsley extracts exhibit antifungal activity with MIC of 4 µL/mL against *Aspergillus parasiticus*. Minimum inhibitory concentrations (MICs) for essential oils from parsley seeds and leaves were 8% and 0.25% against *S. aureus*, 4% and 0.12% against *Vibrio cholera*, 16% and 0.5% against *Yersinia enterocolitica*, and 32% and 1% against *Salmonella enterica* and *Escherichia coli* (Fateme et al. 2010).

Studies on other species of the Apiaceae family have revealed potential biocidal properties against these pathogens. Species such as *Torilis anthriscus*, *Aegopodium podagraria*, and *Daucus carota* have demonstrated antimicrobial activity against bacteria such as *Agrobacterium radiobacter* and *Erwinia carotovora*. In particular, the essential oil of *C. maculatum* (poison hemlock) exhibits antibacterial properties against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Di Napoli et al. 2019). In addition, the essential oil of *E. triquetrum* has significant antibacterial activity against potato blackleg caused by *Pectobacterium atrosepticum* and *Pseudomonas cichorii*, which attacks crops such as lettuce and celery. In contrast, the essential oil of *S. olusatrum* exhibits moderate antibacterial activity (Merad et al. 2021). *Ferulago angulata* from the Apiaceae family has shown variable toxicity against several phytopathogenic bacteria including *Erwinia amylovora* and *Xanthomonas* or (Moghaddam et al. 2018).

In a study by Mabeku et al., both *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments were conducted in rats to evaluate the reduction of bacterial load against six strains using methanolic extracts of *E. foetidum* at 500 mg/kg. The results demonstrated a rich array of metabolites and antipathogenic properties in both experimental conditions, showing comparable efficacy to ciprofloxacin (Mabeku et al. 2016). A similar study highlighted the antibacterial properties of this herb using methanolic extracts, which showed minimum inhibitory concentrations (≥12 mM) against various pathogens including *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Shigella sonnei*, *Shigella dysenteriae*, *Shigella flexneri*, and *Vibrio cholerae* (Panda et al. 2016).

Analysis of *E. foetidum* leaf extract revealed that the biosynthesized ZnO NPs were highly effective against *E. coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus* subsp. *aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (Begum et al. 2018). Furthermore, the combination of chicory with other known medicinal plants from Assam, India, demonstrated enhanced antibacterial and antifungal activities. Notably, a synergistic effect was observed when *E. foetidum* was combined with *Bacopa monnieri* against *S. typhimurium*. The medicinal properties of these plants are believed to be due to the presence of various compounds including alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, steroids, saponins and phenols (Borah et al. 2014). In a related study, Linguaraju et al. demonstrated that the organic solvent ethyl acetate inhibited several bacteria including *E. coli* (with an inhibition

zone of 17 mm), *P. aeruginosa* (28 mm), *Bacillus subtilis* (20 mm), *S. aureus* (25 mm), and the fungus *C. albicans* (18 mm). This was associated with a higher concentration of bioactive compounds (Linguaraju et al. 2016).

In previous studies, essential oils from *F. badrakema* showed moderate efficacy against the Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus cereus*, and the fungus *Candida albicans*, but were ineffective against Gram-negative bacteria such as *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (Sahebkar and Iranshahi 2010). Another study on *F. glauca* found that *Bacillus subtilis* was the most susceptible among Gram-positive bacteria, with moderate activity against *Streptococcus mutans* and *Enterococcus faecalis*, but little activity against *S. aureus* and *C. albicans*. Oils from the leaves and fruits were the most effective. For *F. latisecta*, the polysulfide-rich oil from its fruits showed antibacterial properties against Gram-positive bacteria, especially *B. cereus* and *S. aureus*, and strong inhibitory activity against *C. albicans*. It was also effective against various dermatophytes, especially *Trichophyton rubrum* and *T. verrucosum*. Furthermore, the essential oil from the aerial parts of *F. latisecta* showed significant inhibitory activity against *B. subtilis* and *E. faecalis*, moderate activity against *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, but no activity against other strains (Malekzadeh et al. 2018). The essential oil from the fruits of *F. gummosa* exhibits strong antibacterial and antifungal properties, acting against Gram-positive bacteria such as *S. aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria such as *E. coli*, as well as fungi such as *C. albicans*. The seed oil of *F. gummosa* also exhibits activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, but has limited effect on *P. aeruginosa* (Kouyakhhi et al. 2008). In contrast, *F. szowitsiana* leaf oil was effective against methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* and several Gram-negative bacteria, with MIC values ranging from 0.156 to 1.25 µg/mL, particularly against MRSA. Another study found that *F. szowitsiana* aerial parts oil was most effective against *B. subtilis* compared to other strains tested. Furthermore, *F. assa-foetida* seed oil demonstrated antifungal activity against five *Aspergillus* species, inhibiting all stages of their asexual reproduction (Hassanabadi et al. 2019).

Studies have shown that essential oils obtained from the root and rhizome of *Ferula hermonis* Boiss. have significant effects against various fungal strains, especially dermatophytes such as *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* (Al-Jafari et al. 2011). The major chemical components identified by GC-MS, FID and ¹³C NMR analyses included α-bisabolol, β-farnesene and δ-cadinene. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) and minimum fungicidal concentration (MFC) for *T. mentagrophytes* were 8 µg/mL and 10.25 µg/mL for 3,5-nonadium and JB73, respectively. Furthermore, the study revealed antifungal properties of hydrodistilled essential oil extracted from fresh stems (FS), fresh flowers (FF), dry stems (DS) and dry flowers (DF) of *Ferula vesceritensis* Coss. & Durieu ex Trab. This essential oil was rich in α and β-pinene, α-phellandrene and contained trace amounts of caryophyllene oxide, arisotolene, carotol and elixene (Khajeh et al. 2005).

Hepatoprotective activity

In a study involving profenofos-poisoned mice, it was observed that low-dose administration of cummin successfully restored the normal levels of serum glutamic-pyruvic transaminase (SGPT) and serum glutamic-oxaloacetic transaminase (SGOT). This finding indicates that cummin plays a critical role in mitigating hepatotoxicity at both cellular and biochemical levels. Furthermore, an aqueous ethanol extract of cummin seeds was shown to significantly reduce the levels of SGPT, SGOT, alkaline phosphatase (ALP), and serum total bilirubin (STB) in rats suffering from nimesulide-induced liver injury in a dose-dependent manner. Histopathological analysis of the liver tissue of these rats revealed reduced ballooning, fibrosis, inflammation, and hepatocyte apoptosis, all of which indicate a protective effect of cummin on the liver (Mushtaq et al. 2014). Furthermore, cummin seed powder showed significant hepatoprotective properties in rats with carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced liver injury. Treatment with cummin powder resulted in normalization of urea, bilirubin, and creatinine levels, and significant reduction in ALP and STB, further supporting its hepatoprotective capabilities. Significantly lower levels of lipid peroxidation also suggested that cummin seed powder is effective in combating free radicals (Nishadh et al. 2013).

Recent studies show that *Anisi aetheroleum* may protect against CCl₄-induced fibrosis in rats. Rats given *Anisi aetheroleum* orally for seven weeks showed a decrease in serum liver enzymes (AST, ALT, ALP), restoration of total protein levels, and improvement in lipid profiles including decreased triglycerides, total cholesterol, and LDL-C, while HDL-C decreased. Histopathological analysis confirmed these biochemical improvements (El-Sayed et al. 2015). The protective effects were also confirmed by anise extract n-hexane, which reduced cell death and markers of liver injury in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies, while increasing glutathione levels and decreasing TBARS. However, the hydroalcoholic extract of anise and *Anisi aetheroleum* showed limited protective effects, indicating that hydrophobic compounds such as anethole may be critical for the hepatoprotective effect. Anise extract reduced serum AST and ALT levels compared with the CCl₄ group, but not as effectively as the silibinin control group. Further studies are needed to confirm (Jamshidzadeh et al. 2015).

In a study on rats with CCl₄-induced liver injury, administration of *Foeniculi aetheroleum* resulted in decreased serum AST, ALT, ALP, and bilirubin levels (Özbek et al. 2003). Histopathological evaluations showed that this essential oil could help prevent chronic liver injury and served as a potent hepatoprotective agent against fibrosis. In addition, fennel essential oil was found to enhance the activities of superoxide dismutase (SOD) and catalase (CAT). However, some compounds found in fennel such as stilbene diglucoside trimers and benzoisofuranone derivative did not show significant antioxidant effects (Özbek et al. 2004). Another study showed that *Foeniculi aetheroleum* markedly decreased serum AST and ALT levels while significantly increasing total protein

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of various plant species of Apiaceae family.

Name of plant species	Antibacterial	MIC ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Main antimicrobial	Ref.
<i>Angelica decurrens</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	14.9	ligustilide, ferulic acid, coumarins	Derakhshan et al. 2008
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	14		
<i>Aegopodium podagraria</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	1.25–5.00	quercetin, kaempferol, apigenin, caffeic acid, chlorogenic acid,	Al-Bayati 2008
<i>Aegopodium alpestre</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	3.1	β -caryophyllene	Fatemeh et al. 2010
	<i>Aerogenic bacterium</i>	3.2		
<i>Bulpeurum bicaule</i> Helm	Iron bacteria	275.2	–	Merad et al. 2021
	Purple sulfur bacteria	296.9		
	Methanobacteriae	118.7		
<i>Angelica sylvestris</i>	<i>Enterobacteria aerogenes</i>	1.8	–	Mabeku et al. 2016
	<i>Enterococcus durans</i>	1.8		
	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	1.8		
	<i>Enterococcus faecium</i>	1.8		
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6.3		
	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	6.3		
<i>Angelica palustris</i>	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i>	6.3	–	Begum et al. 2018
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	1.24		
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	1.75		
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	2.04		
<i>Carum carvi</i>	genera <i>Clavibacter</i>	10.33	carvone, limonene, carvacrol, thymol	Rafieian et al. 2024
	<i>Curtobacterium</i>	11.23		
	<i>Rhodococcus</i>	9.83		
	<i>Erwinia</i>	7.32		
	<i>Xanthomonas</i>	11.03		
	<i>Ralstonia</i>	0.83		
	<i>Agrobacterium</i>	0.76		
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	>256.00		
<i>Bulpeurum longifolium</i> L subsp. <i>aureum</i>	<i>Aerogenic bacterium</i>	5	–	Mohsenzadeh 2007
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	15.9		
<i>Bulpeurum multinerve</i>	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>	16.9	limonene	Mandal and Mandal 2015
	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	13.4		
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	27.5–265.00		
<i>Cenolophium denudatum</i>	<i>Enterococcus faecalis</i>	27.5–265.00	apiole, β -phellandrene, γ -terpinene:	Razzaghi-Abyaneh et al. 2009
	<i>Acinetobacter boumannii</i>			
	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>			
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>			
	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>			
<i>Eryngium planum</i> L.	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	22.5	γ -terpinene, β -phellandrene, apiole	Begum et al. 2018
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	27.5		
	<i>Candida albicans</i>	17.8		
<i>Conioselinum tataricum</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	26.50–30.10	γ -terpinene, β -phellandrene, apiole	Sahebkar and Iranshahi 2010
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>			
	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>			
	<i>Candida albicans</i>			
<i>Ferula foetida</i> Bunge	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	175	–	Al-Ja'fari et al. 2011
	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	125		
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	100		
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	100		
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	105		
<i>Heracleum sibiricum</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	100	bergapten, pimpinellin, isopimpinellin, xanthotoxin and imperatorin	Linguaraju et al. 2016
	<i>Candida albicans</i>	0.50–16.00		
<i>Heracleum dissectum</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	27.7	–	Kouyakhhi et al. 2008
	<i>Staphylococcus epidermidis</i>	27.5		
<i>Peucedanum morisonii</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	12.7	peucedanin	Hassanabadi et al. 2019
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	12.9		
	<i>Salmonella typhimurium</i>	11.6		

and albumin levels in rats suffering from CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity. Furthermore, *Foeniculi aetheroleum* supplementation resulted in significant improvements in various biochemical markers including decreased alkaline phosphatase (ALP) levels as well as decreased bilirubin, malondialdehyde (MDA), and superoxide dismutase (SOD) values. This improvement strengthened the antioxidant defense system and reduced the production of excess free radicals (Choi and Hwang 2004). Moreover, rats suffering from CCl₄-induced liver fibrosis that were given oral treatment with *Foeniculi aetheroleum* showed significant protection against elevation of serum liver enzymes such as AST, ALT, and ALP along with improvements in other liver function indices (De Marino et al. 2007). The combination of *Foeniculi aetheroleum* with emamectin benzoate (EB) effectively reduced the hemotoxic, immunotoxic and hepatotoxic effects associated with subchronic EB treatment in male rats. This protective effect is likely due to the antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and hepatoprotective properties of *Foeniculi aetheroleum*. Therefore, the study suggests that this oil may mitigate the toxic effects in individuals exposed to long-term EB (El-Sheikh and Galal 2015a, 2015b). Furthermore, a study on trans-anethole, a key component of *F. vulgare*, indicates its potential to protect the liver against ischemia/reperfusion (I/R) injury by inhibiting interferon regulatory factor-1 (IRF-1) and modulating the release of high-mobility group box 1 (HMGB1), which subsequently affects the activation of toll-like receptors (TLRs) (Cho et al. 2013).

Coriander, both in leaf and seed form, has been shown to reduce thioacetamide-induced liver toxicity as confirmed by histological analysis. Ethanol aqueous-ethanolic extract of coriander leaves provided a dose-dependent protective effect against CCl₄-induced oxidative stress by significantly reducing the levels of serum transaminases (SGOT, SGPT) and TBARs. It also increased liver enzyme activities (SOD, CAT, GPx) in rats, which is comparable to the hepatoprotective drug silymarin (Sreelatha et al. 2009). Addition of coriander seed aqueous extract before paracetamol administration improved the biochemical parameters as confirmed by histopathological evaluations. Furthermore, ethanol extract of *C. sativum* reduced liver weight and enzyme activities (SGOT, SGPT, ALP) and decreased direct bilirubin levels in CCl₄-poisoned animals, reversing fat deposition and necrosis (Ramadan et al. 2013a). A study on Wistar rats showed that pre-treatment with coriander leaf extract significantly increased the activities of SOD, CAT and GPx compared to CCl₄ treatment alone, effectively mitigating its toxic effects. At a dosage of 200 mg/kg, the efficacy of the leaf extract was comparable to silymarin, supporting its traditional use as a liver protectant against oxidative stress (Pandey et al. 2011).

Studies show that methanol extracts from celery seeds exert significant hepatoprotective effects against paracetamol- or thioacetamide-induced liver injury in rats. Liver function tests showed improved liver health with increased quinone reductase, glutathione-S-transferase, and serum gamma-glutamyl transferase activities when rats

were pretreated with celery seed extract prior to hepatocarcinogenesis. Celery root and leaf juices also had positive effects on biochemical parameters and exhibited antioxidant properties when administered with doxorubicin (Singh and Handa 1995). Celery leaf juice decreased serum lipid peroxidases, while root and leaf juices enhanced antioxidant enzyme activities. In addition, celery juice normalized liver function markers and improved antioxidant defense against oxidative stress from lead acetate and gamma radiation. A diet containing dried celery leaf powder reduced liver enzymes and blood lipids in hypercholesterolemic rats, suggesting that inclusion of celery in the diet may be beneficial for liver health (Sultana et al. 2005).

A study on cultivated carrot seed extract showed that pre-treatment significantly decreased the levels of SGPT, SGOT and ALP in animals with thioacetamide-induced oxidative stress. It also increased the activities of antioxidant enzymes (SOD, CAT, GRD, GPx, GST) and decreased lipid peroxidation (LPO), demonstrating strong antioxidant properties (Shoba et al. 2008). The extract protected against hepatocellular injury by paracetamol, isoniazid and alcohol, and decreased plasma AST, ALT and bilirubin levels in a dose-dependent manner in CCl₄ and lindane-induced hepatotoxicity while restoring antioxidant and HDL-cholesterol levels (Bishayee et al. 1995). In addition, kaempferol from carrot seeds normalized serum and liver parameters in paracetamol-treated rats (Balasubramaniam et al. 1998). The methanol-acetone extract of wild carrot showed significant DPPH activity and high iron-reducing antioxidant capacity (FRAP), with the sesquiterpene-rich fraction effectively chelating iron ions (Jain et al. 2012). Pretreatment with this extract counteracted the decrease in SOD, CAT, and GST levels induced by CCl₄, reducing liver injury. These results indicate that wild carrot oil fractions have a unique chemical profile and significant antioxidant and hepatoprotective effects against CCl₄-induced liver toxicity (Shebaby et al. 2015).

Hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effect

Heydari-Majd et al. (2019) investigated *F. gummosa* essential oil (BEO) impregnated zein nanofibers for their effect on α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibition. Key components of BEO such as alpha-pinene and β -myrcene were identified using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC/MS). Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) confirmed the efficient integration of oil into the fibers, achieving around 95% encapsulation efficiency. BEO-loaded nanofibers (1–4% w/w) exhibited significant inhibitory activity against α -amylase (IC₅₀: 1.09–1.64 mg/mL) and α -glucosidase (IC₅₀: 0.78–1.25 mg/mL), indicating their potential as a delivery system for the treatment of diabetes. Another study investigated the effects of essential oils of three medicinal plants, including *F. gummosa*, on streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. Male Wistar rats were given a 45 mg/kg dose

of streptozotocin and treated with 200 mg/kg essential oil daily for 30 days. Analysis using Tukey's test and one-way ANOVA showed that *F. gummosa* treatment resulted in HDL-C, LDL-C, cholesterol, triglyceride and glucose levels of 42.07 ± 9.68 , 29.59 ± 3.76 , 91.02 ± 11.95 , 105.18 ± 12.13 and 429.91 ± 46.14 μM , respectively. The essential oil significantly reduced LDL-C and triglyceride levels, but had no significant effect on glucose levels compared with the diabetic control group (Karimlar et al. 2019).

The hypoglycemic effects of *E. creticum* were investigated by administering an aqueous decoction to normoglycemic and hyperglycemic streptozotocin-induced diabetic rats. They replaced the rats' drinking water with the extract and measured blood glucose levels after 1, 4, and 24 hours. The extract reduced glucose levels in both groups, with a significant reduction observed in the hyperglycemic rats (Jaghabir 1991). Another study narrowed the effects of an aqueous extract of fresh aerial parts of Jordanian *E. creticum* at concentrations up to 50 mg/mL on starch digestion *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Using the Granfeld method, they compared the extract with acarbose, a known α -glucosidase inhibitor, assessing α -amylase and α -amylglucosidase activities. *In vivo*, they monitored blood glucose levels in rats after starch consumption. Although the extract did not significantly affect enzymatic digestion of starch compared to acarbose, it did reduce glucose levels during a starch tolerance test, showing improvements at 90 and 135 minutes post-ingestion. However, it did not improve glucose tolerance, and glycemic curves remained unchanged after a glucose load (Kasabri et al. 2011).

The researchers investigated the effects of an aqueous extract of fresh aerial parts of Jordanian *E. creticum* on pancreatic and extrapancreatic functions. They conducted bioassays to evaluate β -cell proliferation, insulin secretion, and glucose diffusion using the murine insulinoma MIN6 β -cell line. The results showed that the extract significantly enhanced glucose-stimulated insulin secretion (GSIS) and promoted β -cell proliferation in a dose-dependent manner (0.001 to 1.0 mg/mL). These results suggest that *E. creticum* may help address the problem of β -cell loss in diabetes (Kasabri et al. 2012).

Conclusion

This review provides an overview of the current state of research regarding the phytochemical analysis of vari-

ous plants of the Apiaceae family. It highlights that extracts from Apiaceae members are promising sources of natural bioactive compounds that have potential for pharmaceutical, food and cosmetic applications. Furthermore, the chemical constituents, along with the antioxidant and antimicrobial properties exhibited by the essential oils and crude extracts from these plants, offer both experimental and scientific support for their traditional use as home remedies. This highlights the need to further explore their potential for developing innovative, eco-friendly industrial applications.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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